

XENOPHOBIA AND GENDERISM IN U.S. HEALTHCARE AND CERVICAL CANCER
SCREENING AMONG SOUTH KOREAN WOMEN

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Abstract

Korean immigrant women in the United States face many challenges with cervical cancer screenings, a test to detect cancer in the cervix, such as knowledge, cultural beliefs, language, and problems in comprehending the healthcare system. The study reviewed 12 research articles that focused on first-generation Korean immigrant women and the impacts of their gender and race on cervical cancer screening uptake and access. Through this literature review, three main themes of knowledge and awareness, systemic and cultural barriers, and encouragement of cervical cancer screening uptake were found. Results included that low knowledge about mammography and Pap smear tests cause Korean immigrant women less likely to get screened, but it is important to note that increasing knowledge will not change behavior alone. With cultural norms of female purity and stigma around cancer in the cervix area, women feel embarrassed to participate. Language difficulties with communication in the healthcare system produce difficulty in accessing services and help to prevent cervical cancer. Overall, this study emphasizes the need for culturally appropriate intervention methods that can help Korean women with navigating healthcare and gain knowledge on the importance and steps towards accessing primary care providers and cervical cancer screening tests.

Keywords: intersectionality, xenophobia, gender oppression, cervical cancer, healthcare exclusion

Introduction

Social Context of South Korean Immigrant Women

Immigration leads to impactful transformations in an individual's life as they leave behind their family and societal norms of their home country. Many immigrants travel to the United States; specifically, there were around 1 million Korean immigrants in the United States (U.S.) in 2019, making them the 10th largest immigrant group in the U.S.¹ During the period 1965-1980, there was an exponential growth seen among Korean immigrant women in the U.S. with a 2,500% increase in immigrants.¹ Many South Korean women married U.S. servicemen, which led to immigration following the Korean War and coined the name Korean War Brides.² Recently, there are around 1.1 million South Koreans in general.¹

Despite the large amount of South Korean immigrants, there is a lack of research on their health issues and experiences, including language barriers, racial discrimination, domestic violence, and conforming to traditional household roles.³ Korean immigrant women are subject to cultural and societal expectations, as they are expected play the role of the caregiver and homemaker because of their gender and racial background, restricting their ability to prioritizing their own health needs.³ South Korean immigrant women face problems with access to care due to difficulty in navigating the U.S. healthcare system as a result of foreign patients, language barrier and racial discrimination that alters health care access, and gender oppression of women being viewed as caregivers and deprived of their autonomy.¹¹ For example, they have issues with access to cervical cancer screenings that encompasses the systems of oppression.

Xenophobia and Cultural Barriers of the Healthcare System

The xenophobic healthcare exclusion in the U.S. prevents South Korean immigrant women from being comfortable to ask for cervical cancer tests. Language barriers, racial discrimination, and cultural unfamiliarity discourage immigrant women from taking cervical cancer tests, highlighting an issue of xenophobia and normalization of purely English in the U.S. healthcare system. Specifically, 13% of Asian American adults report racial discrimination during health care encounters and around 11% report unfair treatment related to insurance, language barriers, and race.⁴ This relates to the problem South Korean women face as they are more marginalized. Around 24% of Korean American are uninsured compared to 14% of non-

Hispanic whites that are uninsured).⁵ Additionally, less than 50% were screened for cervical cancer screening.⁶ This is concerning given that Korean immigrant women experience higher cervical cancer prevalence rates, at 11.9 per 100,000 women compared to 7.3 for non-Hispanic whites.⁷ Moreover, Korean American women who are unfamiliar with cervical cancer are 3 times less likely to have screened for cervical cancer compared to Korean American women who are familiar with cervical cancer.⁸ The U.S. healthcare system excludes immigrant women with culturally incompetent healthcare that is language and cultural appropriate

Health Outcome of Gender Oppression

Moreover, gender oppression in the U.S. healthcare system affects South Korean immigrant women by reinforcing traditional Korean gender roles and stigmatizing reproductive health and cervical cancer.^{9, 10} Traditional gender norms in South Korean culture link women's private areas of the bodies to motherhood and family duty.⁹ Thus, there is a stigma around cervical cancer within the U.S. healthcare, leading to gender oppression. Korean women are being discouraged from seeking screenings and treatment out of fear of being perceived as lacking in the cultural expectations as a wife or mother.⁹ This issue contributes to accessing cervical cancer screenings and allowing Korean immigrant women to focus on their own reproductive need. Xenophobia in the form of racial discrimination and language exclusion compound with gender oppression such as expectations for women to take the caregiving role over self-care which makes Korean immigrant women more vulnerable in the healthcare system and the barriers they face. Their autonomy and independence are taken away as preventive and reproductive care is discouraged in society and is viewed in a negative light.⁹ The overlapping identities emphasize the vulnerability they face with accessibility to cervical cancer screenings. Addressing this gap of the overlapping oppression is important because it highlights the lived realities that South Korean immigrant women go through relating to both their race and gender.

Intersectionality

This research paper implements the intracategorical approach to intersectionality to understand how intersecting processes of oppression influence cervical cancer screening access for Korean immigrant women. The intersectionality theory emphasizes multiple systems of oppression and how they intersect to influence health outcomes. This theory focuses on people

with overlapping social identities across race, ethnicity, gender, and socioeconomic status. South Korean immigrant women have overlapping identities with being Asian American, women, and low-English proficiency. These intersect to cause xenophobia and genderism within the U.S. healthcare system. Language exclusion and insensitivity towards various cultures reflect the xenophobic structure of healthcare. Cultural norms of modesty rooted from Korea's traditions limit women's access to necessary health care services emphasizing the gender oppression and expectations. These oppressions come into light with South Korean immigrant women and especially shape their access of cervical cancer screenings. The intracategorical intersectionality framework allows the exploration of the complex interconnectedness of xenophobia and genderism in the U.S. healthcare system and explain the lived realities of South Korean immigrant women.

Summary

In sum, South Korean immigrant women faces disparities in cervical cancer screenings. Xenophobia includes the prejudice against those from foreign countries and cultures and in this study, the word means the language and cultural exclusion in the U.S. healthcare systems. Genderism in healthcare is reinforced through Korean cultural norms of modesty and views over a women's body, discouraging Korean women from seeking cervical cancer screenings. The significance of this study is due to the population of South Korean immigrant women who are often understudied in the U.S. healthcare system. Further, South Koreans are the 10st largest immigrant group as stated previously, highlighting the importance of the population selected and why the health outcome is impactful to society. The study focuses on both systems of oppression that work together to create the inaccessibility of cervical cancer screenings. There is lack of existing studies that interconnect xenophobia and genderism in the healthcare system and many studies focus on one system of oppression. To investigate this gap, this study seeks to address the following research question; How do the intersecting systems of xenophobic healthcare exclusion and genderism within the U.S. healthcare system influence access to cervical cancer screenings for South Korean immigrant women?

Sources

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Method Section

The inclusion criteria were as follow: (1) published in a peer-reviewed journal, (2) human data-driven research, (3) written in English, (4) conducted in the United States and related to a healthcare system setting, (5) population included 1st generation South Korean immigrant women, (6) investigate the impact of cervical cancer screening access for South Korean immigrant women and the exposures that influence access, (7) studies done within years 2015-2025. Articles were excluded if they were (1) non-peer-reviewed journal articles, (2) non-data-driven articles, (3) written in Korean, (4) included participants of 2nd generation children of South Korean immigrants, (5) included members of other nationalities. Rationale for exclusion: Studies that included participants of 2nd generation children were excluded because they do not have the same cultural unfamiliarity to the U.S. and the U.S. healthcare system. Additionally, 2nd generation children do not experience the same language barriers as 1st generation women do because they have grown up in the U.S. and thus, they have more exposure. First-generation refers to South Korean women who were born in South Korea and later immigrated to the United States. Members of other nationalities were excluded because the research paper is focused on South Koreans and their specific struggles with cervical cancer screening access.

A literature search was conducted in August 2025 using Google Scholar and PubMed. The main aim of the search was to find studies examining barriers and accessibility of cervical cancer screenings in the U.S. healthcare system for South Korean immigrant women. The first step of the process was to search in Google Scholar for the barriers that South Korean immigrant women faced in the healthcare system in general. This was done to provide a foundation to the issues that arise for Korean women. Keywords used were issues in U.S. healthcare, immigrant health, women health, and South Korean health. Then, the search included a deeper focus into cervical cancer screening barriers and the specific contexts of xenophobia and genderism in the healthcare system. Search terms included Korean immigrant cervical cancer screenings, xenophobia in U.S. healthcare, cervical cancer screening barriers, and cultural norms for Korean women, women's health, U.S. healthcare system, and gender bias in healthcare. These key words were selected based on the inclusion criteria and to narrow down my focus of the research goal.

Synthesis groupings were categorized to find out the influence the U.S. healthcare has on South Korean immigrant women in terms of cervical cancer access. I first conducted a search of the literature to identify the contexts of cervical cancer screenings access. Then, I reviewed each

study to determine whether it related to the exposures of language barriers, cultural unfamiliarity, and gender and cultural norms. Table 1 lists the characteristics of those studies categorized by theme and exposures.

Table 1: Characteristics of Studies

Author	Research Question	Participants	Method	Results/Analysis
<p>Shin, H. Y., Song, S. Y., Jun, J. K., Kim, K. Y., & Kang, P. (2021). Barriers and strategies for cervical cancer screening: What do female university students know and want?. PloS one, 16(10), e0257529. https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0257529</p>	<p>What are the barriers and knowledge level of cervical cancer screenings for female university students?</p>	<p>26 female university students aged 20-29 at metropolitan area's university</p>	<p>Online survey about demographic, sexual experiences, cervical cancer screening history, knowledge about prevention, risk, and symptoms</p>	<p>There is a negative social view about cervical cancer screenings such as parental views and there is insufficient information about the screening. Due to negative views, there is a stigma around cervical cancer screenings and the lack of information and knowledge creates even more unfamiliarity to immigrant women who are culturally unfamiliar. There does not seem to be enough education on cervical cancer screenings and tests which poses a problem if women who</p>

				live in the U.S. do not even have much knowledge.
Lee, H. Y., & Lee, M. H. (2017). Barriers to Cervical Cancer Screening and Prevention in Young Korean Immigrant Women: Implications for Intervention Development. <i>Journal of transcultural nursing : official journal of the Transcultural Nursing Society</i> , 28(4), 353–362.	What are the barriers to Pap test uptake and HPV vaccines?	16 Korean immigrant women in focus groups age 21-29	mScreening intervention, 7-day text message-based intervention	Lack of cultural sensitivity with little to none Korean-speaking providers create a marginalized environment where women struggle to navigate the healthcare system. Women mentioned the importance of intact hymen for unmarried women in Korean culture. This shows the sense of purity in Korean traditions that make cervical cancer screenings seem negative. This study relates to gender oppression as women face this

				healthcare barrier with certain purity standards.
Choi, J. A., & Kim, O. (2022). Cervical Cancer Prevention Education Program for Rural Korean Immigrant Women. <i>Western journal of nursing research</i> , 44(7), 684–691. https://doi.org/10.1177/01939459211014111	How effective is a cervical cancer prevention education program for rural Korean immigrant women?	46 Korean immigrant women who have not been screened in the past three years	Intervention program for experimental group and completed a post-program survey on week 12	The program caused an increased level of knowledge of cervical cancer prevention with a p value of 0.001. However, even after the education program, there was still a stigma from the lack of Korean language services, Korean staff, and booking appointment difficulties. This shows the systemic oppression in the healthcare system that prevents Korean immigrant women from having more access.

<p>Lee, H. Y., Choi, Y. J., Shin, J., Yoon, Y. J., & An, S. (2021). Adherence to Cervical Cancer Screening in Korean American Immigrant Women: Identifying Malleable Variables for Intervention Development. <i>Journal of Transcultural Nursing</i>, 32(3), 230–238. (DOI: 10.1177/1043659620914693)</p>	<p>What are Pap test rates and factors associated with uptake?</p>	<p>230 Korean immigrant women in Atlanta, Georgia</p>	<p>Interviews and self-administered surveys</p>	<p>55.7% of respondents had received a Pap test at least once in their life and less than half with 45.7% received Pap tests within the last three years. Unexpectedly, the findings suggest that English proficiency was not related to Pap tests.</p>
<p>Han, H. R., Lee, Y. J., Min, D., Chepkorir, J., Hwang, D. A., & Chae, S. (2025). Web-Based Delivery of an Effective Church-Based Intervention Program to Promote Cancer Screening (Community-based Health litEracy-focused intervention for breast and cervical Cancer Control) Among Korean Immigrant Women in the United States: Randomized Controlled Trial. <i>JMIR human factors</i>, 12, e66092. https://doi.org/10.2196/66092</p>	<p>What is the feasibility and acceptability of the intervention-e-CHECC-uP (community based health literacy intervention)?</p>	<p>40 Korean immigrant women who are 21-65 year old recruited from Korean churches in Baltimore-Washington Metropolitan area</p>	<p>Study survey with CONSORT and web-based health literacy intervention (CHECC-uP), education module learning with</p>	<p>85% retention rate and screening rates rose around 47.9% Pap tests which shows that barriers can be addressed through cultural and linguistic support.</p>

			trained bilingual staff	
<p>Cha, E. Y., & Chun, H. (2021). Barriers and Challenges to Cervical Cancer Screening, Follow-Up, and Prevention Measures among Korean Immigrant Women in Hawaii. <i>Asia-Pacific journal of oncology nursing</i>, 8(2), 132–138. https://doi.org/10.4103/2347-5625.308302</p>	<p>What are health challenges to cervical cancer screening for Korean immigrants in Hawaii?</p>	<p>In-depth interviews with 20 immigrant women ages 21-65 years old</p>	<p>Recruited using purposeful sampling and interview data was sorted through a data analysis computer software</p>	<p>Linguistic barriers negatively influenced access to health information with 27.5% of women mentioning language barriers in the interviews. If there were services, they were not sufficient due to lack of availability.</p>
<p>Fang, C. Y., Ma, G. X., Handorf, E. A., Feng, Z., Tan, Y., Rhee, J., Miller, S. M., Kim, C., & Koh, H. S. (2017). Addressing multilevel barriers to cervical cancer screening in Korean American women: A randomized trial of a community-based intervention. <i>Cancer</i>, 123(6), 1018–1026. https://doi.org/10.1002/cncr.30391</p>	<p>Are cervical cancer screening rates higher for those in the intervention program?</p>	<p>705 Korean women recruited from 22 churches with 347 receiving the intervention and 358 in</p>	<p>The experiment group was an education program and navigation services and the control received</p>	<p>The intervention program had greater screening rates compared to the control program which shows the community cancer education is key to increase cervical cancer rates. This may go against other studies because it focuses on community</p>

		the control group	general health education.	instead of addressing the cultural and linguistic gaps in the U.S. healthcare system.
Cha, Eurina Yujin, "Korean Immigrant Women's Perceptions of Cervical Cancer Screening in Hawaii" (2018). Walden Dissertations and Doctoral Studies. 5992. https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/dissertations/5992	What are cultural health perceptions and barriers to cervical cancer screenings for Korean women in Hawaii?	20 Korean immigrants aged 21-65 in Hawaii	Conducted interviews and questionnaires	35% of participants reported they did not know what a Pap smear test was, but 65% of participants reported they had received screening even without fully understanding the test. But, 40% of participants had not engaged with the Pap smear test even when they understood cancer screening importance despite having U.S. health insurance and English proficiency.
Lee, M. H., Merighi, J., Cofie, L., & Rogers, B. (2024). Korean American Immigrant Women's	What are the social determinants	240 Korean women who	30-50 minute survey	Having Medicare and insurance were negatively associated with

<p>Mammography Use in Korea: Factors Associated with Medical Tourism. <i>Social Sciences</i>, 13(12), 676. https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci13120676</p>	<p>associated with Korean immigrant women’s mammography use in Korea after immigration to the U.S.?</p>	<p>were born in Korean and immigrated to the U.S. between 40-79 years old in Los Angeles County, California</p>	<p>completed face-to-face or self-administered</p>	<p>mammogram use in Korea after immigration to the U.S. Those who have inconsistent healthcare coverage in the U.S. may seek care in Korea which shows that lack of cultural sensitivity to immigrant women causes them to find healthcare access elsewhere, adding more burden.</p>
<p>Lee, M., Lee, M. A., Ahn, H., Ko, J., Yon, E., Lee, J., ... Braden, C. J. (2021). Health Literacy and Access to Care in Cancer Screening Among Korean Americans. <i>HLRP: Health Literacy Research and Practice</i>, 5(4), e310–e318. https://doi.org/10.3928/24748307-20211104-01 (Original work published October 1, 2021)</p>	<p>What is the impact of health literacy on cancer screening and access to healthcare for Korean immigrants?</p>	<p>377 Korean Americans (Korean immigrants living in the U.S.) who live in Texas and 18 years and older</p>	<p>Paper-based surveys were completed in person who voluntarily came to the booth at Health Fairs</p>	<p>Korean immigrants with health insurance were 3 times as likely to do cancer screenings. Even though the insurance coverage rate of Korean immigrants was 79%, there was no effect on cancer screening or health care service. So, insurance alone is not sufficient. This study does not</p>

				address cervical cancer specifically, causing differences in analysis.
Chawla, N., Breen, N., Liu, B., Lee, R., & Kagawa-Singer, M. (2015). Asian American women in California: a pooled analysis of predictors for breast and cervical cancer screening. <i>American journal of public health</i> , 105(2), e98–e109. https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2014.302250	What are the patterns of cervical cancer screening among Asian American women in California?	7865 Asian American women 21-64 years old	Pooled data from 5 cycles of CHIS (digital health survey)	Korean women had the lowest Pap test rates and mammography rates. The study found that time in the U.S. was associated with higher screening rates for Korean immigrants.
Choi, Y. J., Lee, H. Y., An, S., Yoon, Y. J., & Oh, J. (2020). Predictors of cervical cancer screening awareness and literacy among korean-american women. <i>Journal of Racial and Ethnic Health Disparities</i> , 7(1), 1-9. doi: https://doi.org/10.1007/s40615-019-00628-2	What are the levels of cervical cancer screening awareness and literacy and associated factors among Korean women in the U.S.?	230 Korean women in metro area in Southeastern state, U.S. who were 18 and older	Self-administered questionnaires for women less 60 years old and group questionnaires for those older than 60	Annual checkups and support are important factors to increase cervical cancer literacy.

Results

Study Selection

A total of 15 articles were initially selected for full article review through the search. After eliminating 5 articles, the final number of selected articles that met the full inclusion criteria was 12. The other 3 did not meet the full inclusion criteria because the studies included Korean American adults, meaning they were not first-generation immigrants and rather, second generation immigrants who have had longer residency in the U.S. Another study excluded was not directly related to cervical cancer screenings and instead focused on other aspects of the U.S. healthcare system unrelated to the current study research question. Ultimately, the 12 articles that met the full study inclusion criteria were characterized by samples of first-generation Korean immigrants, related to cervical cancer screenings, and focusing on aspects of gender oppression and xenophobia.

Characteristics of Included Studies

The 12 studies included took place in the United States as the participants are first-generation Korean immigrants. Studies took place in the United States, including urban, suburban, and rural cities which shows the diverse geographical contexts. Several studies were situated in metropolitan areas such as Los Angeles (Lee et al., 2021), metro-Atlanta (Lee et al., 2018), Baltimore-Washington area (Han et al., 2017), and an unspecified Southeastern state (Choi et al., 2020). Other studies focused on rural settings (Choi & Kim, 2019) and Hawaii (Cha, 2013; Cha & Chun, 2015). Broader contexts were also included in studies (Shin et al., 2021; Fang et al., 2017; Chawla et al., 2019). Nine of the twelve studies were asking about the barriers of cervical cancer screenings, Pap smear uptake, or mammography use (Lee & Lee, 2017; Cha & Chun, 2021; Lee et al., 2024). The other three studies were about awareness and knowledge of cervical cancer screenings, dealing with solutions of interventions and community projects to assess South Korean women (Choi & Kim, 2022; Han et al., 2025; Fang et al., 2017). Eight studies were qualitative studies, most being focus groups, questionnaires, or face-to-face interviews that assessed Korean immigrants' feelings about cervical cancer screening. Three studies used quantitative approaches with the use of surveys and statistical analyses (Lee et al., 2021; Chawla et al., 2015; Choi & Kim, 2022) while one had a mixed-method design that combined a quantitative online survey with focus group interviews (Shin et al., 2021).

Remaining research papers used a more qualitative approach with focus groups to develop specific themes of health interventions (Lee & Lee, 2017).

Participant Characteristics

The participants across included studies were Korean immigrant adults, all above 18 years old. The range for the sample average age across the studies were 18-65 years old. All participants were women and born in South Korea. However, one study was studied cervical cancer trends across six Asian nationalities with Koreans being at most risk and vulnerable to cervical cancer (Chawla et al. 2015). Cha & Chun (2021) specified the educational degree of the participants as majority were college-level educated and other studies had more participants highly educated with a range of 12-20 years of education (Lee et al., 2021). The sample size range of participants varied from 16 (Lee & Lee, 2017) to 230 (Choi et al., 2020). Most studies were conducted in the metropolitan area rather than rural and more low-income areas.

Synthesis of Findings Across Studies

Across the twelve studies, there is a repeated pattern of participants who are Korean immigrant women that face a multitude of barriers to cervical cancer screening such as knowledge, language, cultural beliefs, and gender. There is also a pattern of culturally tailored community intervention programs improving cervical cancer screening knowledge and uptake. (Choi & Kim, 2022; Han et al., 2025; Fang et al., 2017). A consistent trend emerges as knowledge about cervical cancer screening among South Korean immigrant women is generally low (Shin et al., 2021; Cha, 2018). Educational programs were shown to improve knowledge, but stigma in society and Korean values around cervical cancer limits the engagement, making Korean immigrant women uncomfortable (Choi & Kim, 2022). However, Cha makes an unexpected finding that even when Korean immigrant women understood cancer screenings, they still did not undergo Pap smears which contrasts with other studies that knowledge would lead to increased screening (Shin et al., 2021; Choi & Kim, 2022; Choi et al., 2020). Together, these studies show that awareness is important for Korean immigrant women, but there are more underlying factors of stigma that plays a role in screening behavior (Choi & Kim, 2022; Han et al., 2025; Fang et al., 2017; Shin et al., 2021; Cha, 2018; Choi et al., 2020).

Studies consistently showed that there is a theme of systemic and cultural barriers, such as access to healthcare and gender oppression, relating to cervical cancer screening among South Korean immigrant women. Lee & Lee (2017) found that there was a lack of cultural sensitivity with barely any Korean speaking providers accessible to Korean women navigating the unfamiliar U.S. healthcare system. There is also purity in Korean traditions with an intact hymen for unmarried women, leading cervical cancer screenings appear negative (Lee & Lee, 2017). This purity influences the healthcare system by creating barriers for cervical cancer screenings and unequal standards for men and women. Similarly, Lee et al. (2024) explored how Korean immigrant women who had their first mammography in the United States is less likely to return to Korea for another screening, pointing towards the idea that challenges in the U.S. healthcare system may cause Korean women to travel to cervical cancer screening services in South Korea. Cha & Chun (2021) shows another cultural barrier of how linguistic shortcomings influence access to health information as access to health coordinators or community health workers with the same language as patients increase cultural interventions and engagement with healthcare services. Nevertheless, Han et al. (2025) concludes that English proficiency and language alone does not directly increase cervical cancer screenings as his study using a digital, e-CHECC-uP, program combines culturally tailored health education, community partnerships, and community health workers alone.

Results from four included studies shows a pattern that encouraging cervical cancer screening uptake among Korean immigrant women is more than just access as it also deals with health insurance and intervention. Lee et al. (2021) found that Korean women with health insurance are more likely to do cancer screenings, but insurance alone did not guarantee uptake as even those with health insurance had low health literacy. A combination of health literacy education, culturally sensitive support, and communication efforts is needed, not just insurance (Lee et al., 2021). Fang et al. (2017) and Han et al. (2025) provided evidence that targeted programs work as they reported higher screening rates after intervention methods of education sessions by community health educators at church centers and a web-based health literacy education program with monthly phone counseling. Chawla et al. (2015) found that time in the U.S. was associated with higher screenings, but Korean women still had the lowest Pap smear test rates among other Asian American women studied (Chinese, Filipino, Japanese, South

Asian, Vietnamese, Cambodian, etc.). Thus, time in the U.S. can help with cervical cancer screening access, but Korean immigrant women still face cultural and language barriers as the healthcare system is not accommodating to all nationalities. Together, these studies suggest that improvements to screening uptake come from multi-level interventions of insurance access, health literacy, and education programs.

Several studies found that the United States healthcare system produces unique barriers that are faced specifically by Korean immigrant women related to overlapping oppression (Lee & Lee 2017; Cha 2018; Cha & Chun 2021; Shin et al. 2021). Cha & Chun (2021) reported that English proficiency alone did not predict screening behavior, showing that it is not just linguistic support that is sufficient to help with cervical cancer screening access. Together, the studies highlight the importance of addressing intersectional barriers to increase cervical cancer screening uptake for Korean immigrant women.

Table 2: Synthesis of Study Findings on Cervical Cancer Screening Access

Theme	Studies Supporting	Summary of Findings	Notes on Differences
Knowledge and Awareness of Cervical Cancer Awareness	Shin et al. (2021), Choi & Kim (2022), Choi et al. (2020)	Korean immigrant women have low cervical cancer screening knowledge and generally, education programs can improve awareness.	Cha (2018) found that awareness on cervical cancer screenings alone does not guarantee participation, pointing towards other factors influencing behavior more.
Systemic and Cultural Barriers	Lee & Lee (2017), Cha & Chun (2021), Lee et al. (2024)	Cultural norms, gender expectations, language, and	No differences were noted.

		healthcare inconsistency create specific obstacles to cervical cancer screenings.	
Encouraging Screening Uptake	Lee et al. (2021), Han et al. (2025), Fang et al. (2017), Chawla et al. (2015)	Multi-level interventions are most effective at increasing cervical cancer screening rates.	Simple intervention methods such as English proficiency and language does not directly lead to cervical cancer screenings (Han et al. 2025).
Intersectionality	Lee & Lee 2017; Cha 2018; Cha & Chun 2021; Shin et al. 2021	Studies found that immigrant women face more discrimination in the healthcare system and more barriers that impact their ability to take Pap smear tests and mammography tests.	Findings were consistent across studies.

Discussion

The purpose of this study was to explore the intersectionality of xenophobia and gender oppression and its effects on Korean immigrant women and their access to cervical cancer screening. Findings reveal that cultural norms, language barriers, and low health literacy for Korean immigrant women cause a detrimental consequence on cervical cancer screening tests such as mammography use and Pap smear tests. Nonetheless, language barriers alone were not statistically significant when account for the effects of intervention and education programs tailored towards language and culture which signifies the impact of community-based programs on screening behaviors. Furthermore, the lack of health literacy, insurance, culturally and linguistic tailored support, and sensitivity were stressors associated with fear and uncomfortable feelings with accessing cervical cancer screenings within the U.S. healthcare system.

Regarding low knowledge and awareness of cervical cancer screening among South Korean immigrant women, findings are consistent with research on low knowledge and awareness of cervical cancer screening among Korean immigrant women (Shin et al., 2021; Choi & Kim, 2022; Choi et al., 2020). My results show new information that even when women may understand the importance of Pap smear and getting tested for cervical cancer, knowledge alone is not sufficient to increase screening uptake. Other prior studies that emphasize language as the primary challenges while the findings in this paper indicate that it is language alone that can fully explain the low screening rates among Korean immigrant women. Like Cha (2018), this study found that a combination of cervical cancer screening uptake is crucial to address the needs of Korean immigrant women (gender oppression and cultural sensitivity).

Findings are consistent with previous research showing the negative impacts of systemic and cultural norms for Korean immigrant women on cervical cancer screenings (Lee & Lee, 2017; Cha & Chun, 2021; Han et al., 2025). My findings show new information about there needs to be a combination of knowledge, cultural sensitivity, and attention towards purity traditions to effectively address screening uptake. Even when language or insurance access is available alone, gender expectations and gendered stigma limit cervical cancer screening participation.

Like previously stated, this paper's findings suggest that encouraging cervical cancer screening requires a multitude and complex strategies rather than single interventions due to the intricate barriers that Korean immigrant women face. They face low health literacy issues, contradiction with purity traditional values, stigma, and access issues which are barriers that cannot be remedied through just literacy knowledge, access to insurance, or translation services alone. Past studies have implied that literacy programs, community partnerships, web-based literacy help, and church-based outreach for Korean immigrant women are helpful and supportive interventions which this study supports (Fang et al., 2017; Han et al., 2025; Lee et al., 2021).

The study's findings suggest important potential public health implications for consideration towards supporting 1st generation South Korean immigrant women which can be strengthened through study replication with larger samples. From past studies that showed that culturally tailored health programs of cervical cancer screenings, health programs may want to improve screening participations through eHealth or online technology use in the digital age (Han et al., 2025), messages containing the benefits of screenings especially for women who have embarrassment about cervical cancer (Fang et al., 2017), Korean-speaking staff, and encouragement for participants to receive regular checkups (Choi & Kim, 2022). Health care providers can use this information to design specific interventions for 1st generation immigrant women and address the stigma in areas such as churches. Additionally, policymakers can help mitigate the oppression in the healthcare system by expanding more linguistic services and literacy resources to provide comprehensive support options for Korean women.

More research and interventions are needed to understand and address the intersectional gender oppression and xenophobia mental health needs of Korean immigrant women. 1st generation immigrants with the inability to speak well and being compounded by traditional gender norms in society overlap creating extra barriers in relation with cervical cancer screening uptake. There is a great need for culturally sensitivity towards Asian Americans and gender equality efforts to address the genderism-related and racism-related stressors. Findings overall convey that the lack of support for genders and immigrants with language and cultural barriers have a unique impact on U.S. healthcare service knowledge and access. Therefore, these

stressors may have long-term implications for Korean immigrants' health, lifespan, and comfort in the U.S.

The study has limitations to consider. The sample size only includes a small amount of research studies, so the findings may not entirely represent all Korean immigrant women in the U.S. Moreover, some of the studies used to analyze the intersectionality collected data through self-reported surveys or interviews, meaning the participants may not have answered the questions accurately. The participants may have felt uncomfortable expressing their true feelings about the realities of the healthcare system to the researchers. Most of the studies used in this paper focused on Korean immigrants in urban areas such as Los Angeles, Texas, and the Washington area which may not reflect experiences of rural areas with women who may face even more barriers to cervical cancer screenings financially. Although the study has its shortcomings, it provides useful insights towards certain cultural programs that are specifically targeted towards knowledge, awareness, and comfort in the U.S. healthcare system.

Future research can include larger groups of Korean immigrant women and more research studies to explore more on education programs, specifically on the components of these programs for community workers and hospitals to know the steps to increase cervical cancer screening uptake. Studies can also look at 1st generation Korean women in different parts of the United States especially in low-income and rural areas to compare the experiences and their feelings about the U.S. healthcare system. In addition, the study sample was 1st generation Korean women, but did not include 2nd generation Korean women. Future researchers could compare these two groups of first generation and second generation to investigate differences of being born in Korea or the United States. Overall, this study adds to our understanding of the U.S. healthcare system regarding cervical cancer screenings and highlights the need for more support towards Korean immigrant women.